

BEAUTY COMMUNICATION; THE IMPORTANCE OF THE COMMUNICATION INTO THE BEAUTY FIELD

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Abstract

The presented study is considered as a research, developed in order to be like a “radiography” of the *Beauty Communication concept*. Its method based on, is meta - analytical and the targeted purpose is to build the foundation of a beauty communication, qualified and specialised, also to highlight few of the components of the Beauty Communication concept. The main conclusion reached is that, into the current reality, there is a distinct communication language, with the main purpose to reach beauty objectives such as cosmetology, aesthetic consultancy, makeup, eyebrow design, body remodelling, hairstyling, manicure, pedicure, spa relaxation techniques & well being. This specialised communication, developed in order to reach & accomplish the beauty objectives, we are considering to be called as “*Beauty communication*”.

Keywords: *beauty, beautician, beauty field, beauty domain, spa, well being, beauty language, beauty communication.*

1. Introduction

The preoccupation for *beauty* and *beauty through health* was, even from the Antiquity, one of the preoccupation which increased together with the development of different civilisations and societies, in general. Without saying chronologically exact time when the first “Beauty Manual” has appeared, we definitely noticed an extraordinary proliferation of beauty manuals, skincare and beauty advices books, during 21st century. Among them we may mention few, such us: Scott, 1973; Sassoon, Sassoon & Duhé, 1975; Romm, 1989; Morris, 1999; Raichur & Cohn, 1999; Neal-Barnett et al, 2000; Masterson, 2014; Park, 2021. In Neal-Barnett et al. (2000) it was mentioned a book published in 1900, with beauty as main objective: *Walker, MCJ (1900). The Madame CJ Walker beauty manual: A thorough treatise covering all branches of beauty culture.* Indianapolis. On the other part, A. Ramsbrock (2015) speaks about “*a science of beauty*”. We must take into consideration that, since thousand years, the preoccupation for beauty and the beauty themes were one of the favourite, into the general frame of discussions between women.

With other words, we may say that Beauty has evolved along with the society. In the current times, Beauty is integrated into the economic circuits, even if we are talking about products which maintain health (and implicit, beauty), or we are talking about services which help to beauty preservation, beauty restoration, or services which “create” beauty. The last category is under the influence of the “so called” Beauty Standards - a common set of “fashion rules” or proportions, under the direct influence of fashion, regarding aesthetic surgery.

In the last century, simultaneously with the technological & industrial development, it was noticed a “boom” of all beauty’s aspects, having as a natural consequence, the creation and, unprecedentedly, the rapid expansion of the Beauty Industry.

The Beauty industry has several main directions, if we take into consideration the final “consumer” or client. Among them, we may mention:

- professional lines dedicated to the beauty salons / spas/ clinics use, for the specialists from the beauty field - factories or laboratories which are manufacturing beauty products (cosmetic products, Nutri - cosmetics, cosmetics accessories or other products related to this topic) for the specialists from the beauty field. Usually, this professional lines are characterized with a greater concentration of active ingredients, comparing with the cosmetic lines produced for the regular customer;

- products destined to the regular customer - here we may find:
 - exclusives lines (bio, organic, vegan, created by stars, singers, actors, even by so-called influencers);
 - luxury lines;
 - retail lines (specialised location, perfumeries, drugstores, beauty points, beauty sites;
 - professional lines created from the same brands which are producing the professional Beauty salon lines with the purpose that customer to maintain a longer time the effect of the ingredients received during beauty treatments / procedures;
 - dermato - pharmaceutical lines available in pharmacies and medical clinics, for the customer with special care needs;
 - mass market lines, characterised by low prices, usually available at supermarkets.

If we take into consideration that ALL those directions are targeting the final customer: people with different ages, sexes, races, education, religions, professions, values, believes, financial and social levels, more or less interested about technology, from different geographic areas, we definitely understand **the importance of proper communication**, in order the products to reach their final customers.

2. Beauty and communication

„The communication plays an important role into the process of product reaching its customer. Can be a communication realised with the help of media channels (tv, radio, internet, social media, magazines, newspapers, specialists or research publications), or a customised direct communication such as:

- conferences, symposiums;
- presentations or launchings of the new beauty products (with audience or “one to one” presentations);
- sampling;
- beauty consultancy sessions etc.

Being a specific, relatively new language, the **Beauty Communication** has developed into a close interdependence with the people’s preoccupation for the art of beauty, and reach an extraordinary impact, simultaneously with the rapid growth of the beauty industry. If the invariable subject of beauty is omnipresent into almost all discussions between two or more women, using a regular language, definitely *for the professional beauty specialist, the proper communication with the client is a must*, if we are talking about aestheticians / beauticians, makeup artist, lash artist, eyebrow designers, hair stylist, nail stylists, beauty products merchandisers, pharmacists, beauty products sale agents, beauty advisers, aesthetic councillors, image consultants or any other subjects involved into the beauty field. If we are taking as example, the communication in the beauty salons or clinics, we have to highlight the reasons why the proper communication is vital and may bring their contribution to the increase of revenues:

- the beauty specialist should know how to communicate efficiently. Even from the first point of discussion, that may be the appointments made via mobile phone (oral or written). Some examples related with this topic may be: phone calls, text messages WhatsApp, Facebook, Messenger, Instagram, Viber, Telegram, in order to provide to the customer pertinent information, concerning the beauty product or service;
- to offer viable alternatives for other services or products, in case when offer is neither valid nor available anymore;
- to know how to suggest and offer other time intervals for appointments, than those from the initial request;
- the beauty specialists should have excellent communication skills verbal or non-verbal, for welcoming the clients, to introduce them into the beauty saloon’s , spa’s or clinic’s atmosphere;
- to know how the offer the exact information needed, regarding the preliminary procedures;

- to use all their communication abilities in order to do an efficient diagnose, to inform about possible contra - indications, the procedure's steps, post - procedure indications, recommended home-use products, needed to maintain longer the effect of the procedure or beauty service performed;

- to maintain an excellent communication with the clients / customers and after treatment / procedure, with the purpose to obtain a feedback regarding the beauty product's effect, quality of the performed beauty procedure / beauty service or any other beauty news relevant for the customer.

From my own 20 years professional experience into the aesthetic field with Romanian and international customers, also 13 years as Beauty trainer, I've noticed the acute need for the improvement of communication abilities into the beauty salons, spas, clinics, not only at front desk / receptionist level (or the person who is doing the customer's appointments), but also at the level of the specialist who is performing the beauty procedure. This specialist has a direct connection with the final customer from the chain *beauty product / beauty service - client*, so the excellent communication skills are highly needed.

As a valid example: In 2009 I have founded the first Spa from South Romania - Aquarium Spa Center, in Slatina - a small city with almost 50.000 inhabitants, with a medium to low salary level. Being inaugurated during the 2008 - 2009 economic crises, in a private and quiet zone of the city, but with no traffic or commercial advantage, the prognoses weren't optimistic.

Instead to follow the common and usual marketing pathways, together with the Spa's team, using efficient communication, we have created, an unique spa's identity: being defined as a fusion between a "Day Spa" and a "Medical Spa", an unique concept for those days.

First of all, everything was built and created with the help of an excellent communication:

- **visual communication of the spa's concept**

- the team, their leader and the visual identity, reflected non - verbally into the visual aspects of them in front of the customers (physical aspects, uniforms)

- The decorations elements and the personalization of the services, according to the aquatic / marine spa's theme concept

team m- tembers communication, in order to mediate the conflicts, to build a solid team, with their members connected to the same values;

- **communication trainings for the team members**, with the goal of an excellent communication *specialist - customer*

Personal development trainings & team buildings, with the purpose of increasing empathy and communication skills, highly necessary to intuit and

preview the customers needs, to identify their communication languages and to be able to adapt to their needs.

During 13 years, with thousands of customers experiencing the spa's beauty & health services, we may definitely say some conclusions regarding the importance of the communication, especially into the beauty business. Finally, *the result of successfully achieving a beauty objective, is highly interrelated with the excellent communication "specialist - customer" and vice versa*. If the client feels that his beauty needs were successfully anticipated or fulfilled and he found in the specialist a reliable "partner", even the imperfections can be forgiven or unnoticeable. But, if a beauty specialist is not successful in establishing a good communication and eventually a good connection with the client / customer, he(she) may present him in vain the most efficient or advanced beauty products or services: the client will neither buy nor try them! This can happen for a simple reason: his(her) emotions will lead him in the majority of the exemplified situations, especially that an educated customer, as nowadays is, will expect, demand, and is total entitled to receive beauty services, via an excellent communication.

The communication skills are expected and required in equal measure, also into the communication between *Sales Agent / Beauty Representative and the Beauty specialist*. In this case, actually, the beauty specialist is *"the customer"* itself. Usually, an educated, specialised "client", with high expectation from the sales agent.

As a trainer for several Beauty cosmetics lines, I've noticed immediately the importance of Beauty sales agents speeches or discourses.

If he is a good communicator (verbal and non verbal), he may be able to convince the power decision person to:

- introduce a new cosmetic / beauty line in the beauty salon / spa / clinic;
- change the existing line with the one that he is representing;
- increase the trust accorded to the specific beauty brand, that they are representing.
- gaining the loyalty of the beauty specialists, making them love the beauty products, they will transmit their enthusiasm or trust, regarding the beauty product, to the final customer.

As a future prediction, the communication in the beauty field, will have a key role in the success of beauty business, in the actual ambiguous economical, political and social context.

3. Conclusions and future research

After unprecedented time of lock down, restrictions, limitations of individual liberties, with the level of stress and panic increased, the beauty consumers orientated to health, relaxation, elimination of the stress, self esteem increase-ment, with the help of procedures which help to obtain the beauty's maintenance,

a better or ideal body shape, the people will highly appreciate an excellent *human - to - human* communication, also a better anticipation and understanding of their needs. Having this in mind, as a future objective, for bringing my professional and academical contribution to the development of this new concept **Beauty Communication**, I will investigate the most important aspects of the communications at the specialist - beauty consumer level, in order to help for the improvement and discovering new paths, which lead to success, harmony, professional and personal satisfaction.

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